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**SUCCESS FACTORS FOR UNIVERSITY INDUSTRY TECHNOLOGY
TRANSFERS: EVIDENCE FROM THE UNIVERSITY OF SRI
JAYEWARDENEPURA, SRI LANKA**

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Abstract: Technology transfer between universities and industries has long been regarded as the pinnacle of science and innovation strategy. Governments encourage universities and businesses to work collaboratively on research initiatives, consultancy and advisory programs to increase their respective capacities for innovation and commercialization of technologies and products. The Triple Helix Model emphasizes the contribution of the university network in transferring knowledge and technology to develop merchantable products and services, rather not confining to conventional teaching and research functions. This study aims to determine the success factors governing the University-industry Technology Transfers (UITT) that occurred recently (2018 to 2022) between the university of Sri Jayewardenepura and the external stakeholders. All the cases reported on the UBL cell official website of the University of Sri Jayewardenepura were considered for the current study. The cases of the UITT process were delineated under three main categories; (i) ready to commercialize technologies (9 cases) (ii) consultancy and advisory (not defined) and (iii) research and development (11 cases). We conducted face-to-face interviews with the Director and the Manager of the UBL Cell of the University of Sri Jayewardenepura and the responsible stakeholders under the cases being studied. The collected data were analysed qualitatively using critical reviewing and content analysis techniques. The key success factors of UITT were commercialization opportunities, university incentives, highly qualified and well-experienced academic staff, and/or curricular valorization including prestige, reputation and visibility. The most frequently reported obstacles included rigid academic policies and negotiations with businesses, lack of funds for research and development activities to further expand the invention into a marketable form, and the limited commercial potential of a patent. In conclusion, effective collaborations between universities and enterprises seemed favourable in all three categories of the University-industry Technology Transfer that had been studied. Further, the present study opens up new arenas and acts as a guide for successful future UITT programs between universities and external stakeholders.

Keywords: University-industry Technology Transfer; Triple Helix Model; Success factors; Sri Lanka